

P60 | Analysis of the antibiotic resistance genes of microorganisms in the milk of cows and goats

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In 2018, 158 cow milk samples and 21 goat milk samples from animals with subclinical mastitis from various farms in five regions of Russia were examined. The objective of the research was to identify DNA of pathogenic bacteria in the milk and to determine the presence of antibiotic resistance genes. We have conducted PCR studies of the biological material on the device "RotorGene-3000" (Australia), using a set of reagents "IDS" (Russia). In 94.3% of cow milk samples, the DNA of the following microorganisms was detected: *Staphylococcus* spp. (73.4%), *S. aureus* (23.4%), *E. coli* (34.1%), *S. agalactiae* (12.0%). The blaDHA gene, which determines resistance to inhibitor-protected penicillins and cephalosporins of the 3rd and 4th generations, was found in 83.0% of *E. coli*. Antimicrobial resistance of *S. aureus* against 2nd generation cephalosporins (MecA gene) was found in 29.2% of the samples. The gene of resistance to macrolides of the 1st generation (ErmB) was found in 20.0% of *Staphylococcus* spp. and 2.7% of *S. agalactiae*. Resistance gene for 1st generation cephalosporins (CTX-M) was found in 3.3% of *E. coli*. In 71.4% of goat milk samples, the following specific microbial DNA was detected: *Staphylococcus* spp. (23.8%), *S. aureus* (38.0%), *E. coli* (42.8%), *S. agalactiae* (9.5%). The blaDHA gene was found in 90.0% of *E. coli*. These data indicate a widespread antibiotic resistance of pathogenic agents in the milk of cows and goats. The high prevalence of blaDHA gene positive samples could be associated with the frequent use of penicillins and cephalosporins of the 3rd and 4th generations on the farms. Laboratory control of bacterial resistance to antibiotics is required. Improvement of udder health management including vaccines or alternative antibiotics should be considered.

P61 | The use of marker vaccines against IBR to control reproduction of dairy herds

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Eradication of bovine herpesvirus (BHV-1, responsible for infectious bovine rhinotracheitis = IBR) in dairy herds is optimally controlled using DIVA-strategy (differentiate infected from vaccinated animals). Differentiation of field and vaccine strains was performed using modified BHV-1-based monovaccines with a deletion of the gE gene. The recovery control was performed with gE and gB diagnostic ELISA test systems, where the gE gene encodes glycoprotein E, which is a virulence factor for all known Alphaherpesvirinae viruses, gB-vaccine marker, which is absent in the field strain. The effects of labeled vaccines on the reproduction in dairy herd with

seroprevalence to a field strain were evaluated. It was found that with the use of labeled vaccines against IBR, seroprevalence of the wild strain in the herd decreased from 95% to 53% during the first year, and it has decreased to 14% during the second year after the start of vaccination. In 5 years the seroprevalence decreased to 5%. Regarding the reproductive performance, it was found that, with the introduction of vaccination against IBR, the period from calving to conception decreased significantly by 11.5% (from 130 to 115 days), the number of placental retentions decreased significantly from 21.9% to 15%. The number of abortions and calves born alive remained unchanged. The use of monovaccine for the prevention of IBR also makes it possible to reduce the appearance of infectious vulvovaginitis: before vaccination against IBR, 52.5% of the cows in the herd had clinical signs of vulvovaginitis (swelling of the vulva, pustules, redness). After the use of monovaccines against IBR, the prevalence of cows with vulvovaginitis was 7%.

P62 | Testing of natural antioxidant oregonin on ram semen quality

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Oregonin is a natural polyphenol, isolated from the *Alnus incana* bark, which possesses antioxidative and anti-inflammatory activities. The objective of this study was to test the effect of different doses of oregonin on the ram semen quality. The ejaculates were collected by artificial vagina from 3 rams. A sperm concentration was adjusted to 200 × 10⁶ cells/ml by dilution with a commercial extender (Triladyl) without oregonin (control) or with 100 μM, 200 μM, 500 μM and 5 mM of oregonin. After that, equal aliquots from all semen samples were stored in a water bath at 37° C for six hours. Motility (CASA), plasma membrane integrity and morphological defects (eosin/nigrosine staining) were estimated at 0, 2 and 6 h after the final dilution. Non parametric Wilcoxon pairs test was used for the statistical analysis. In oregonin treated samples, the progressive motility increased for 4% (100 μM) and 6% (500 μM and 5 mM) between 0 h and 6 h compared to the control. The VCL (curvilinear velocity) and percent of linear moving sperm were enhanced for 9.1% (100 μM) and 6.7% (500 μM and 5 mM) and for 4.3% (100 μM) and 2.7% (500 μM and 5 mM) respectively at 2 h of the storage. There were no significant differences in the morphological defects (abnormal tail and cytoplasmic drops) between control and treated groups in average (6.35 ± 0.8% vs. 6.80 ± 0.73%; 3.20 ± 0.62 vs. 2.6 ± 0.81%). The plasma membrane integrity was 17% higher in average in the experimental samples compared to the control